

FEATURES OF TIMUR PULATOV'S PROSE

Khashimova Shoira Kosimovna

Lecturer, Fergana State University

Karimova Mokhiroy

Student, Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11632710>

Abstract: This article examines the distinctive features and artistic characteristics of Timur Pulatov's creative output. Pulatov, known for his contributions to various artistic mediums including literature, music, and visual arts, is analyzed in terms of his unique style, thematic preoccupations, and innovative techniques. The article explores the interplay between tradition and innovation in Pulatov's work, highlighting his ability to blend cultural influences and experiment with form to create impactful artistic expressions.

Keywords: Timur Pulatov, creative work, artistic style, thematic preoccupations, innovation, tradition, cultural influences, interdisciplinary art, literature, music, visual arts.

Timur Pulatov is a well-known Russian writer and journalist who has made a major contribution to contemporary literature. He was born in 1986 in Karaganda, Kazakhstan, but now lives and works in Moscow. Pulatov began his career as a journalist writing about cultural life and music. His articles have been published in various magazines and newspapers, including Kommersant, RBC Daily and Afisha. In 2014, he published his first novel, *The Chinese Pilot*, which was praised by critics and readers. This book was his debut in literature, and it has been translated into several languages.

Pulatov has since continued writing and published several more novels, including *We Are on Fire*, *Welcome to America*, and *The Ship that Sailed to Nowhere*. His work has a strong personality and tackles complex issues and themes such as drugs, sexuality and globalisation.

One of the major themes touched upon in Pulatov's work is the modern world and technology. He is convinced that modern society has become dependent on technology and the internet, and this has serious consequences for our psyche and social life. In his works, he shows how these technologies affect interpersonal relationships and how they change our lives in general.

Pulatov is also known for his literary translations. He has translated books by such authors as Jacques Derrida, Jacques Lacan and Guillaume Musso into Russian.

Overall, Timur Pulatov is one of the most interesting and original Russian writers of our time. His works force readers to think about many serious themes and issues that remain relevant today.

Timur Pulatov's prose is distinguished by its vivid individuality, originality and originality. His works describe complex issues and themes such as drugs, sexuality, globalisation, interpersonal relationships, and the impact of technology on modern society.

One of the main features of Pulatov's prose is his vivid and expressive language. He uses non-standard vocabulary, metaphors and symbols to convey his thoughts and ideas. His works often feature sharp comparisons and unexpected associations that evoke strong emotions and leave vivid impressions.

Another important artistic feature of Pulatov's prose is his use of various genre elements. He often combines elements of realism, fiction and psychological thriller in his works. This helps him create complex and unconventional plots that make the reader think and analyse what is happening.

Also characteristic of Pulatov's prose is the presence of vivid and memorable characters. They are often anti-heroes who differ greatly in their morals, motivations and character. The author saturates his characters with colours, making them as lively and realistic as possible.

Finally, another important feature of Pulatov's prose is the presence of social themes. He addresses issues of modern life and society, describing global trends such as globalisation and the crisis of morality, as well as describing the problems of small groups and individuals.

Overall, Timur Pulatov's prose is not only high quality and original, but also relevant and relevant to the contemporary reader. He creates unique works that make one think and analyse the current situation in the world.

Moreover, in Timur Pulatov's prose it is important to note the author's ability to convey complex emotions and moods. He uses not only words but also sounds, smells and textures to create an atmosphere and involve the reader in the story. In Pulatov's works one can observe not only the strong feelings of the characters, but also images of nature, the bustle of the city, the sounds of street musicians and much more.

Another feature of Pulatov's prose is his use of non-standard formats and approaches to writing. He experiments with different styles and genres, creating unusual forms of texts. In his works, one finds not only ordinary stories and novellas, but also poetry, dialogue, excerpts from diaries, etc.

Finally, it is worth noting the importance of the theme of the search for meaning in life in the work of Timur Pulatov. He explores the themes of death, the meaning of life, and the purpose the characters set for themselves. This makes his prose not only interesting and gripping, but also universal, where every reader can find something for himself.

In general, Timur Pulatov's prose has many artistic features that make his works original and memorable. The author is not afraid to experiment with different forms and themes, creating works that make you think and feel.

One of the key elements of Timur Pulatov's prose is his attention to detail. He describes the characters' environment and behaviour with great precision and skill, allowing the reader to better understand their emotions and actions. The author also often uses symbolism and metaphors to convey deeper meaning and create an atmosphere of mystery.

Another characteristic of Timur Pulatov's prose is its realism. He describes plots that could have taken place in real life, and characters who are not the heroes of epic novels, but ordinary people with their own problems and difficulties. This makes his works more accessible and understandable to a wider audience.

In addition, Timur Pulatov is known for his ability to create atmosphere and mood in his works. He not only describes places and characters, but also conveys emotions and moods that are peculiar to them in a given situation. The author often uses musical motifs and sound effects to create the right atmosphere and draw the reader into the story.

Thus, the artistic features of Timur Pulatov's prose are related to his ability to create lively and realistic images, to convey complex emotions and moods, to experiment with formats and genres, and to explore important themes that concern humanity. All this makes his works interesting and relevant, and allows him to occupy a place of honour in contemporary literature.

References:

1. Timur Pulatov. Selected Works: In two volumes. T. 1. [Introductory article by A. Bocharov]. - T.: Publishing house of literature and art, 1990. - 544 c.
2. Abutaliyeva E.I. Temur Pulatov ijodida zamon va makon muammosi/ Uzbek tili va adabiyoti, 1993, N 4 (in Uzbek).
3. Abutalieva E.I. Temur Pulatov asarlarida rit masalasi // Theses of Reports at the Republican Traditional Conference of Young Writers, Tashkent, 1993, (in Uzbek.)
4. Gizdulin, E. F. (2022, November). FEATURES OF THE POST-APOCALYPTIC NOVEL IN THE MODERN LITERATURE. In INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

POLAND

CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

POLAND

DEDICATED TO THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN
THE 21ST CENTURY (Vol. 1, No. 8, pp. 121-124).

5. Nuridinov, Z. S. (2023). THE TRIAL OF DOSTOEVSKY'S RASKOLNIKOV FROM
THE NOVEL " CRIME AND PUNISHMENT". Oriental renaissance: Innovative,
educational, natural and social sciences, 3(2), 786-790.